

D3.2 - Report on Edge AI functional and non- functional requirements

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
ADR	AI, Data and Robotics
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
AI-aaS	AI-as-a-Service
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hub
EIC	European Innovation Council
EIF	European Investment Fund
EU	European Union
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
HW	Hardware
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
ISS	International Space Station
JPL	Jet Propulsion Laboratory
LLM	Large Language Model
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NoE	Network of Excellence

ODM	Original Design Manufacturer
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OS	Operating System
RISC	Reduced Instruction Set Computer
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SRA	Strategic Research Agenda
SW	Software
TDW	Theme Development Workshop
TEF	Testing and Experimentation Facility
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

Executive Summary

The deliverable D3.2, “Report on Edge AI functional and non-functional requirements” presents a comprehensive exploration/investigation of functional and non-functional requirements (including ethical and legal considerations) of edge AI systems, providing insights into the holistic view of these systems across hardware, software, the AI technology stack, and data applied to AI-based technologies and applications across the micro-, deep-, and meta-edge continuum. The deliverable is currently being extended to include more details and definitions and will be published as a monograph in this year by River Publishers, Denmark. The publication will be the Open Access and available both online and in printing format. The publication is a detailed written study focused on functional and non-functional requirements for edge AI systems to provide an overview of current state of play, concepts, definitions, taxonomy and gaps in the field.

Edge AI systems are characterised by several properties, such as functionality, performance, cost, dependability, and trustworthiness.

This deliverable interlinks the definition of functional and non-functional requirements of edge AI systems with the concepts of edge AI system dependability and trustworthiness.

Dependability is fundamental to the performance of edge AI systems and reflects their operational requirements. In real-time edge AI systems, dependability is the ability to provide services that can be trusted within a time period. The dependability of an edge AI system reflects the degree of trustworthiness in the system. Trustworthiness is the ability of an edge AI system to meet functional and non-functional requirements in a verifiable way, meaning that it can be checked for correctness by a person or tool.

Establishing trustworthiness in edge AI involves collaboration across technical, ethical, and regulatory domains. It is a continuous effort that requires defining the functional and non-functional requirements, their key performance indicators (KPIs), measures, monitoring, ongoing assessment, transparency, and alignment with societal values and needs.

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1. Introduction

Edge AI represents a paradigm shift in deploying and utilising AI technologies, marking a transformative evolution from centralised data processing systems to decentralised, edge-oriented solutions. This transition underscores the capability of executing AI algorithms directly on intelligent edge devices and embedded systems across the edge continuum, including micro-, deep and meta-edge, including avoiding the need for constant connectivity to cloud-based processing centres. As edge AI is developed and applied across various sectors, understanding the edge AI system's functional and non-functional requirements becomes imperative to harness the full potential of technology.

This paper aims to structure and explain the comprehensive set of requirements essential for the successful realisation of edge AI systems.

The functional requirements discussed address the core features, capabilities and tasks that edge AI systems perform to fulfil their intended purpose. These capabilities are critical considering the performance, latency, bandwidth, response times, energy efficiency, data processing, machine learning and deep learning model execution and real-time decision-making at the edge.

The non-functional requirements focus on edge AI systems' quality attributes or characteristics that impact the performance. Topics such as availability, connectability, maintainability, privacy, reliability, resilience, safety, security, and AI-specific attributes, e.g., accountability, accuracy, authenticity, credibility, controllability, compliance, durability, efficiency, explainability, fairness, inclusiveness, integrity, interpretability, interoperability, learnability, performance, robustness, transparency, understandability, usability are analysed to provide a holistic view of what is needed to ensure that edge AI systems can operate effectively in diverse and often constrained environments.

By delineating these requirements, the paper provides stakeholders, including researchers, designers, developers, system architects, and decision-makers, with a framework for designing and implementing edge AI solutions that meet operational objectives while delivering sustained value and efficiency. As we delve into the specifics of these requirements, the analysis highlights the challenges and opportunities associated with deploying AI at the edge yet guiding efforts to leverage this transformative technology in real-world applications.

The paper defines the functional and non-functional requirements and provides examples of their KPIs, measures (quantitative, qualitative), monitoring, ongoing assessment, transparency, and alignment with societal values and needs.

The paper links the definition of functional and non-functional requirements of edge AI systems with the concepts of edge AI system dependability and trustworthiness.

Dependability is essential to the performance of real-time edge AI systems and reflects edge AI systems' operational requirements while reflecting the degree of trustworthiness in the system. As a result, trustworthiness is the ability of an edge AI system to meet functional and non-functional requirements in a verifiable way, meaning that it can be checked for correctness by a person or tool

through verification, validation, testing, and benchmarking and supported by explainability and interpretability methods.

2. Taxonomy and Terminology

The objective of this section is to provide an overview of taxonomy, terminology and definitions of AI and edge AI terms and concepts, which are essential for clear communication, systematic analysis, development of a strategic research agenda, innovation, regulation, business strategy, interdisciplinary collaboration, effective deployment and standardisation. It lays the foundation for the coherent and unified progress of the field.

Having standard definitions and terminology for AI and edge AI terms and concepts prevents miscommunications and misinterpretations arising from varying interpretations of terms, establishing a common baseline for discussions and ensuring that the stakeholders involved have a clear understanding of the key concepts.

Taxonomy allows the classification of different AI and Edge AI methods, algorithms, and systems, making it easier to address and analyse them systematically by helping in effectively evaluating, comparing, and benchmarking different approaches, technologies, solutions, and applications.

A clear taxonomy can support identifying gaps in current research and areas that need further exploration and provide a solid foundation upon which new ideas, models, and technologies can be built.

Using a common taxonomy, terminology and definitions of AI and edge AI terms and concepts helps regulators and policymakers create appropriate frameworks, guidelines, and standards to ensure the ethical and safe development and deployment of AI and edge AI technologies, ensuring compliance and responsible AI deployment.

Edge AI applied to different industrial domains requires interdisciplinary collaboration, as the technology's development intersects with various fields, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), sensing/actuating, edge computing, cybersecurity, and intelligent connectivity.

Understanding the definitions and taxonomy can help identify the most suitable AI or Edge AI techniques for specific real-world applications, optimise performance, and ensure practical feasibility.

2.1. Definitions

In this section, we propose definitions for the main concepts related to AI and edge AI considering that the challenge with a definition is that it specifies the meaning or significance of a word or phrase and can concern either its usage or the content of a concept expressed by a word.

Definition challenges often arise due to the inherent complexity and variability of the scientific and technological domain, as well as the different terminologies used in other domains.

Moreover, as technology and science evolve, so do their terminology and definitions, resulting in shifts in meaning that can render previously clear definitions outdated or incomplete. This dynamic nature of terminology requires continuous adaptation and consensus, which can be challenging to

achieve across the scientific and industrial domains, especially in rapidly advancing or inherently subjective fields, such as AI technology.

2.1.1. Artificial Intelligence

Many AI researchers acknowledge that defining intelligence in a universally satisfactory manner is challenging. However, for the field to advance coherently, it is essential to reason from a clear and generally accepted statement of its subject matter. Despite the lack of a standardised definition of intelligence in AI today, establishing a common framework is crucial for guiding research, fostering communication, and ensuring consistent progress in the discipline.

In this context, several definitions of artificial intelligence and machine intelligence exist as listed in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1: AI definitions.

	AI Definition
1	Artificial intelligence is that activity devoted to making machines intelligent, and intelligence is that quality that enables an entity to function appropriately and with foresight in its environment [46].
2	The study of agents that receive percepts from the environment and perform actions [47].
3	The science of making machines do things that would require intelligence if done by humans [39].
4	The use of computer programs and programming techniques to cast light on the principles of intelligence in general and human thought in particular [39].
5	Artificial Intelligence is a science and a set of computational technologies that are by inspired by-but typically operate quite from differently from-the ways people use their nervous systems and bodies to sense, learn, reason, and take action [43].
6	Intelligence is the capacity of an information-processing system to adapt to its environment while operating with insufficient knowledge and resources [54].
7	Artificial Intelligence is a fully controlled agent with a capacity of an information-processing system to adapt to its environment while operating with insufficient knowledge and resources [53].
8	Artificial intelligence may be considered a computational construct, as it is inferred from the outcomes of simulated aspects of human thought and decision-making, which are facilitated by data processing, machine learning techniques, and algorithmic principles [41].
9	Intelligence is the computational part of the ability to achieve goals. A goal achieving system is one that is more usefully understood in terms of outcomes than in terms of mechanisms [44].
10	AI is a machine’s ability to perform logical analysis, acquire knowledge, and adapt to an industrial environment that varies over time or in context. These abilities include the collective attributes of a machine (i.e., computer, robot, or intelligent IoT device) to perform functions such as perception, understanding, reason, prediction, learning, decision making and action [1].
11	Artificial intelligence (AI) is the discipline of research and development of mechanisms and applications of AI systems. Research and development can take place across any number of fields such as computer science, data science, humanities, mathematics and natural sciences [18].

12 Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to systems that display intelligent behaviour by analysing their environment and taking actions – with some degree of autonomy – to achieve specific goals. AI-based systems can be purely software-based, acting in the virtual world (e.g., voice assistants, image analysis software, search engines, speech and face recognition systems), or AI can be embedded in hardware devices (e.g., advanced robots, autonomous vehicles, drones or Internet of Things (IoT) applications) [11][12][13][14].[11][12][13][14]

AI system: An AI system is a machine-based system that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments. Different AI systems vary in their levels of autonomy and adaptiveness after deployment [60].

AI training: Is defined as the process to determine or to improve the parameters of a machine learning model, based on a machine learning algorithm, by using training data [18].

AI inference: Reasoning by which conclusions are derived from known premises. A premise is either a fact, a rule, a model, a feature or raw data [18].

The edge AI definition builds on the converge of AI, IoT and edge computing technologies and is defined later in this section. It is useful to note that that in continual learning, training and inference stages are no longer purely subsequent, but more heavily intertwined.

2.1.2. Open-source

Open source is a paradigm and practice that promotes the free access, use, and modification of software, hardware, or other resources. It emphasises collaboration, transparency, and community-driven development. Open source typically involves distributing the source code or design files, allowing users to study, modify, and improve the product. This approach fosters innovation and inclusivity, enabling diverse contributions and widespread adoption.

Open-source hardware centres on making physical design files and documentation available for replication and modification. Open-source software focuses on freely accessible source code and the ability to modify and redistribute software. Open-source AI involves sharing code, models, and datasets for collaborative advancement, emphasising ethical considerations and transparency.

The most widely recognised definitions of open source are the ones provided by the Open Source Initiative (OSI) [65], which maintains a set of criteria for what constitutes open-source software and now open-source, and the Open Source Hardware Association (OSHW) [66] which maintains the definition and set of standards for open-source hardware.

The AI and edge AI developers are supporting open-source developments, and the European Commission is increasingly reinforcing the open accessibility of research outputs, including data, code, hardware and publications [61]. This push is part of the broader Open Science policy, aiming to make research more transparent, efficient, and impactful. Open access promotes better science and innovation in both public and private sectors. The Open Research Europe platform provides guidelines for authors on managing and sharing their research data[62]. These guidelines emphasise the importance of making data openly accessible and reusable. This European platform endorses

the **FAIR** principles that emphasise making data **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable [63].

2.1.2.1 Open-source Hardware

The Open Source Hardware Association (OSHW) provides a widely recognized definition and set of standards for open-source hardware [66]. The definition is based on the Open Source Definition for Open Source Software [65].

Open Source Hardware (OSHW) refers to tangible artifacts—such as machines, devices, or other physical things—whose design has been released to the public so that anyone can make, modify, distribute, and use it. This definition aims to provide guidelines for developing and evaluating licenses for Open Source Hardware.

Hardware differs from software in that physical resources must always be committed to creating physical goods. Therefore, individuals or companies producing items (“products”) under an OSHW license have an obligation to make it clear that such products are not manufactured, sold, warranted, or otherwise sanctioned by the original designer and not to make use of any trademarks owned by the original designer.

The distribution terms of Open Source Hardware must comply with the following criteria [66]:

- **Documentation** - The hardware must be released with documentation including design files and must allow modification and distribution of the design files. Where documentation is not furnished with the physical product, there must be a well-publicized means of obtaining this documentation for no more than a reasonable reproduction cost, preferably downloading via the Internet without charge. The documentation must include design files in the preferred format for making changes, such as the native file format of a CAD program. Deliberately obfuscated design files are not allowed. Intermediate forms analogous to compiled computer code—such as printer-ready copper artwork from a CAD program—are not allowed as substitutes. The license may require that the design files are provided in fully-documented, open format(s).
- **Scope** - The hardware documentation must clearly specify what portion of the design, if not all, is being released under the license.
- **Necessary Software** - If the licensed design requires software, embedded or otherwise, to operate properly and fulfill its essential functions, then the license may require that one of the following conditions be met:
 - The interfaces are sufficiently documented that it could reasonably be considered straightforward to write open-source software that allows the device to operate properly and fulfill its essential functions. For example, this may include using detailed signal timing diagrams or pseudocode to clearly illustrate the interface in operation.
 - The necessary software is released under an OSI-approved open-source license.
- **Derived Works** - The license shall allow modifications and derived works to be distributed under the same terms as the license of the original work. The license shall also allow for the

manufacture, sale, distribution, and use of products created from the design files, the design files themselves, and derivatives thereof.

- **Free redistribution** - The license shall not restrict any party from selling or giving away the project documentation. It shall not require a royalty or other fee for such sale or for the sale of derived works.
- **Attribution** - The license may require derived documents and copyright notices associated with devices to provide attribution to the licensors when distributing design files, manufactured products, and/or derivatives thereof. The license may require that this information be accessible to the end-user using the device typically but shall not specify a specific format of display. The license may require derived works to carry a different name or version number from the original design.
- **No Discrimination Against Persons or Groups** - The license must not discriminate against any person or group of persons.
- **No Discrimination Against Fields of Endeavor** - The license must not restrict anyone from using the work (including manufactured hardware) in a specific field of endeavour. For example, it must not restrict the hardware from being used in a business or from being used in nuclear research.
- **Distribution of License** - The rights granted by the license must apply to all to whom the work is redistributed without the need for execution of an additional license by those parties.
- **License Must Not Be Specific to a Product** - The rights granted by the license must not depend on the licensed work being part of a particular product. If a portion is extracted from a work and used or distributed within the terms of the license, all parties to whom that work is redistributed should have the same rights as those that are granted for the original work.
- **License Must Not Restrict Other Hardware or Software** - License Must Not Restrict Other Hardware or Software: The license must not place restrictions on other items that are aggregated with the licensed work but not derivative of it. For example, the license must not insist that all other hardware sold with the licensed item be open source, nor that only open-source software be used external to the device.
- **License Must Be Technology-Neutral** - License Must Be Technology-Neutral: No license provision may be predicated on any individual technology, specific part, or component.

On the hardware side, RISC-V plays a crucial role in the open-source movement [79]. RISC-V is an open standard Instruction Set Architecture (ISA) which allows anyone to design and sell RISC-V-based chips without licensing fees, fostering innovation and competition. Its flexibility and customizability make it suitable for various applications, from embedded systems to high-performance computing and AI. This inclusivity makes it easier for smaller companies to enter the market and encourages the use of open-source hardware, allowing high-performance computing to become available to a larger audience. Other open-source hardware platforms for AI are:

- **BeagleBone** [80]: An open-source development board that offers a powerful platform for AI and machine learning applications.

- **Raspberry Pi** [81]: The Raspberry Pi is a low-cost, credit-card-sized computer that can be used for a variety of AI projects. Its affordability and versatility make it an excellent choice for hobbyists and educators looking to explore AI. Although the Raspberry Pi itself is not entirely open source, its schematics are regularly released as documentation, and it does support and contribute to the open-source community.
- **ESP32** [82]: The core ESP32 hardware, developed by Espressif Systems, is proprietary. However, there are open-source hardware versions available, such as the ESP32-EVB by Olimex.
- **Antmicro's Open-Source Jetson Baseboard** [83]: There are open-source projects and community contributions that enhance the Jetson ecosystem. Antmicro has developed an open-source Jetson baseboard to allow customers to get full control of the solutions that we build based on it, along with unmatched flexibility, transparency and usability.
- **Eyes of Things (EoT) Project** [78]: The schematics of the EoT board were made public on the project's website. However, the main blocks, like the Myriad processor, were not disclosed.

2.1.2.2 Open-source Software

According to the Open Source Initiative, open-source software must comply with the following criteria:

- **Free Redistribution:** The software can be freely distributed to anyone without restrictions, including both source code and compiled binaries.
- **Source Code:** The source code must be included or made available, allowing users to modify and improve the software.
- **Modification:** Users must be able to modify the software to suit their needs. This includes the ability to create derivative works.
- **Integrity of the Author's Source Code:** Distributions of modified versions may be allowed only if they are clearly marked and not misrepresented as the original software.
- **Non-Discrimination Against Persons or Groups:** The license must not discriminate against any person or group of persons.
- **Non-Discrimination Against Fields of Endeavor:** The license must not restrict anyone from using the software in a specific field of endeavour, such as business or research.
- **Distribution of License:** The rights attached to the software must apply to all who receive it, making it unnecessary to sign further agreements.
- **License Must Not Be Specific to a Product:** The rights attached to the software must not depend on the software being part of a particular product.
- **The License Must Not Restrict Other Software:** The license should not impose restrictions on other software distributed along with the open-source software.
- **Technology-Neutral:** No provision of the license may be predicated on any individual technology or style of interface.

Open-source software is built on several key principles:

- **Collaboration:** Open source encourages collaborative development, allowing developers from different backgrounds to contribute to and improve the software.

- **Transparency:** With access to source code, users can understand how the software operates, which fosters trust and accountability.
- **Community-Driven:** Open-source projects often rely on communities of users and developers who advocate for improvements and support one another.
- **Innovation:** Open-source promotes innovation by allowing anyone to build upon existing software, leading to rapid development cycles and diverse applications.
- **Access and Inclusion:** By removing cost barriers and restrictions, open-source software is accessible to a wide range of users, including those in developing countries.
- These principles help to create a dynamic ecosystem where software can evolve and adapt to meet the needs of its users while promoting inclusivity and collaboration.

2.1.2.3 Open-source AI

[64][67][64][68][67][67]In [69], the potential of open-source AI and their critical challenges are highlighted. On the positive side, open-source AI can enhance transparency and facilitate the auditing of AI systems, which in turn can build citizen trust. It also stimulates economic activities and fosters domain-specific expertise by allowing both the public and private sectors to innovate more freely. However, legal challenges arise from the need to navigate complex intellectual property rights and licensing issues. Another drawback is that maintaining and updating AI projects can be demanding, requiring substantial resources and expertise. Data-related challenges include ensuring the availability of high-quality datasets and addressing privacy concerns. Risk management is another critical area, as open-source AI systems can be more vulnerable to security threats. Additionally, societal and ethical challenges must be considered, such as the potential for bias in AI systems and the broader implications of AI deployment on society.

Open-source hardware and software have revolutionized the field of artificial intelligence (AI), making advanced technologies more accessible and fostering innovation through community collaboration. Thus, we can claim that it is not only the advent of deep learning and powerful GPUs what have caused the AI explosion, but also the widespread access to research results, code and datasets. An open-source AI ecosystem has helped lower the barriers for researchers, students and practitioners to acquire AI skills and develop prototypes of new exciting ideas. Some well-known examples of open-source software for AI include:

- **TensorFlow and PyTorch** [70][71]: Developed by Google and Facebook's AI Research lab respectively, they are two of the most prominent open source frameworks for AI. They offer a comprehensive ecosystem of tools, libraries, and community resources that support a large variety of AI applications.
- **Keras** [72]: Keras is a high-level neural networks API, written in Python and capable of running on top of TensorFlow, Microsoft Cognitive Toolkit, Theano, or PlaidML. It allows for easy and fast prototyping, making it a popular choice for beginners and experts alike.
- **Hugging Face** [73]: It is known for its open-source contributions. The company provides a suite of tools, including the popular Transformers library, which offers pre-trained models for tasks such as text classification, translation, and summarization. Hugging Face's commitment to open-

source AI is evident in its extensive model hub, where developers can share and access a wide range of models and datasets.

- **OpenCV** [74]: It is one of the most well-known and widely used computer vision libraries in the world. Its extensive collection of algorithms and tools makes it a go-to choose for both beginners and experts in the field of computer vision. Since OpenCV 3.1 there is DNN module in the library that implements inferencing with deep AI networks, facilitating the integration of AI solutions in computer vision applications.
- **Gymnasium** [75]: Gymnasium is an open source Python library for developing and comparing reinforcement learning algorithms by providing a standard API to communicate between learning algorithms and environments, as well as a standard set of environments compliant with that API. Gymnasium is a fork of OpenAI's Gym library.
- **NVIDIA Jetson open-source components** [76]: Although the hardware is proprietary, some tools and libraries associated with Jetson are open source. For example, jetson-stats is an open-source package for monitoring and controlling Jetson devices.
- **PYNQ** [77]: An open-source project from Xilinx that makes it easy to design embedded systems with Python and programmable logic.
- **Eyes of Things (EoT) Project** [78]: EoT was an Innovation Action funded under the European Union's H2020 Framework Programme that built an open embedded computer vision platform with AI capabilities. The generated code was made public at the end of the project.
- **Lightweight Kubernetes (K3s)**: K3s is a certified lightweight Kubernetes distribution that automates application software deployment to Edge AI devices.

Within the ongoing AI arms race (present almost every day in mass media), big companies are eager to get traction and publicity via open sourcing part of their work. Independent of this, the open-source paradigm can indeed be profitable within the field of AI. Take for example the case of company OpenAI, which started with the explicit aim to develop open and safe artificial intelligence for humanity. A few years later, however, OpenAI transitioned to a capped-profit model, citing the need for substantial funding and competitive advantage [84]. This shift highlights the tension between open-source ideals and the practical demands of sustaining advanced AI research and development. Balancing openness with financial viability remains a significant challenge in the AI industry.

As another example, the aforementioned EoT project (which was coordinated by dAIEdge partner UCLM) made its software open on the project's website and some companies showed interest, downloaded it, and contacted the consortium to ask how they could run and test it. Part of this software, and the open board designed, was later used by the company Ubotica Technologies (also part of dAIEdge) for their project developments. Particularly, the EoT board was used by Ubotica on the AI-enabled Earth observation satellite, PhiSat-1. This satellite, part of a European Space Agency (ESA) program, this AI technology to process data directly on-board, leading to faster and more efficient applications [85]. Achievements like this highlight how open-source projects can promote innovation and business within the AI industry.

Another example is a firearm detection dataset created recently by UCLM. A portion of this dataset was made public and described in [86]. Subsequently, a video surveillance company showed interest in the complete dataset and purchased it under a license.

These examples demonstrate how the open-source approach can attract commercial interest and generate revenue, proving that it is a viable and profitable model in the field of artificial intelligence.

However, what truly constitutes "open source" in the context of AI remains an open question. Addressing this question is crucial because it impacts how AI technologies are developed, shared, and used globally. Key points of the discussion to define open-source AI are [64]:

- **Accessibility:** Open-source AI tools allow individuals and organizations with limited resources to experiment with and develop AI technologies.
- **Collaboration:** Open-source projects foster a collaborative environment where developers can share ideas, improve existing tools, and create innovative solutions.
- **Transparency:** Open-source software and hardware promote transparency, enabling users to understand how AI models work and ensuring that they can be audited for fairness and bias.
- **Customization:** Users can modify open-source tools to suit their specific needs, leading to more appropriate and effective AI solutions.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** Open-source projects reduce the cost of development by providing free access to high-quality tools and resources.
- **Ethical and Legal Considerations:** This includes concerns about the misuse of AI technologies and the need for regulations to ensure responsible use.

The need for a specific definition of open-source AI arises from the unique characteristics of AI systems compared to traditional software. AI systems involve not just code, but also models, training data, and weights. Without a clear definition, some entities might misuse the term "open source" for marketing purposes, leading to confusion and potentially undermining trust in AI technologies.

The Open source Initiative (OSI) has been working since mid-2023 to create a clear definition of open source AI [67], based on OECD's definition of AI [60]. This involves ensuring that AI systems are transparent, modifiable, and shareable, adhering to the principles of open-source software. OSI has brought together researchers, lawyers, policymakers, activists, and representatives from major tech companies like Meta, Google, and Amazon [64]. Having a diverse group is essential to ensure that the definition is robust and widely accepted, helping to find a balance between different perspectives and interests [68].

The current draft of OSI's "Open-Source AI Definition" emphasizes four fundamental freedoms [67]:

- **Freely Usable:** The AI components should be freely usable by anyone for any purpose.
- **Understandable:** Users need to know how AI systems were created and work.
- **Modifiable:** Users should be able to modify AI systems to suit their needs.
- **Shareable:** AI systems, with or without modifications, should be shareable with others, promoting further innovation and collaboration.

Additionally, AI systems require transparency regarding their training data, source code, and models, ensuring that researchers can inspect and understand the systems. This level of transparency is crucial for building trust in AI systems to reuse and modify them. To modify an AI system, the following needs to be considered [67]:

- **Data Information:** Detailed data information is required to recreate an AI system. This includes training methodologies, data sets, gathering process, scope, characteristics, selection process, labelling, and curating methods. Data must be available under licenses that comply with the Open-Source Definition.
- **Code:** Source code for training and running the AI system must be available with OSI-approved licenses.
- **Weights:** Model weights and parameters must be available under OSI-approved terms.

The current draft also makes a distinction between open-source AI models and weights. An AI model includes the architecture, parameters (weights), and inference code, while AI weights are the learned parameters that overlay the model architecture.

Given dAIEdge's commitment to promoting open and ethical AI, there is a possibility that the project eventually contributes to the definition of open-source AI. Contributing to this definition would align with dAIEdge's goals of fostering innovation, transparency, and collaboration in the AI community. A clear and universally accepted definition can help ensure that AI technologies are developed and used in ways that benefit society.

2.1.3. Edge Computing

Edge computing is a distributed computing paradigm that brings computation and data storage closer to the location where they are needed to improve response times and save bandwidth. Edge computing processes data locally on or near the device that generated it, such as IoT devices, sensors, or local on-premises servers.

Figure 2-1: Edge granularity. [48]

The key features of edge computing are the proximity to where the data is generated reducing latency and enabling faster processing, while providing bandwidth efficiency by reducing the amount of data that needs to be transmitted to a central data processing. This allows for real-time processing with minimal delays, scalable growth as devices and data volumes increase and enhanced security and privacy by keeping sensitive data closer to its source and controlling data flow to centralised systems.

2.1.4. Micro-Edge

Micro-edge is defined as the miniaturised version of edge computing, implemented where the sensing/actuating computational resources and capabilities are deployed into microdevices. The concept pushes processing and analytics to be performed on micro, lightweight, and outer resource-constrained devices compared to single-board computers and gateways. These devices may distil information from the data collected by integrating AI-based algorithms for inference and training. Intelligent micro-edge allows real-time applications to become omnipresent and react quickly and intelligently to inferred situations while consuming minimal power.

The micro-edge includes intelligent sensors (physical, chemical, environmental parameters, perception, etc.) and actuators (audio, motion, etc.) systems with processing and connectivity capabilities that generate insight data and analytics. Micro-edge devices are implemented using microcontrollers built around ARM Cortex M0, M0+, M3, M4, M7X, ASICs and RISC V. The distance from the data source (sensors/actuators) is minimised, and the micro-edge devices have extreme constraints on cost and power consumption.

2.1.5. Deep-Edge

Deep-edge involves deploying advanced computational resources and AI capabilities at the edges of networks. The deep-edge model emphasises processing data in real-time, close to the data source, involving more complex computationally intensive applications than the micro-edge. Deep-edge devices have a higher power budget since they are shared across multiple endpoints, and generally have a more capable processor which can be multiplexed to support those endpoints.

The deep-edge comprises intelligent controllers, PLCs, SCADA elements, connected machine vision systems, networking equipment, gateways, and computing units that aggregate data from the sensors/actuators and IoT devices. Deep-edge processing capabilities are implemented with performant processors and microcontrollers, such as Intel i-series, Atom, ARM Cortex M7+, etc., including CPUs, GPUs, TPUs, FPGAs and ASICs. The system architecture, including the deep edge, relies on foreseen functionality and deployment options. These functions include cognitive capabilities that can acquire, aggregate, understand, react to data, exchange, and distribute information.

Deep-edge computing enables a new level of AI-driven analysis and autonomy at the extreme edges of networks, supporting the growing demand for responsive, intelligent, and decentralised data processing across various sectors.

2.1.6. Meta-Edge

Meta-edge computing enables a high level of edge processing and AI-driven analysis on high performance processors and on-premises servers emphasising enhanced integration, scalability,

and coordination across edge computing continuum. Meta-edge offers adaptability to changing conditions and requirements, such as fluctuating workloads, network conditions, or data flows, adjusting resource deployment and task execution accordingly while generating higher-level insights or decisions that require understanding or context from broader data sets.

The meta-edge integrates processing units, typically on-premises, implemented with high-performance embedded computing units, edge machine vision systems, and edge servers (e.g., high-performance CPUs, GPUs, FPGAs, etc.), which are designed to handle compute-intensive tasks (e.g., data series, image, and video processing), advanced analytics, AI-based functions, networking, and data storage.

Meta-edge aggregates data and insights from multiple edge nodes, creating a meta-level understanding or intelligence that can inform broader network or enterprise-level decisions.

2.1.7. Edge AI

Edge AI combines AI, IoT and edge computing technologies and provides real-time collection, computing, and analytics, allowing data processing and execution of AI algorithms to occur directly on devices at the network's edge. By bringing AI closer to the source of data generation, edge AI enables more efficient and responsive decision-making in various applications.

Edge AI uses AI-based algorithms and techniques on edge devices, enabling more rapid and efficient data processing and improved privacy and security. Edge AI provides computational intelligence to develop intelligent systems that perform real-time tasks that typically require human-level intelligence, such as decision-making, problem-solving, pattern recognition, and learning.

By combining AI's analytical capabilities with the IoT's sensing/actuating capabilities, intelligent connectivity, and the distributed architecture of edge computing, edge AI offers robust, efficient, and secure solutions across diverse industries, supporting the growing demand for intelligent and autonomous systems.

2.1.8. Edge AI System Dependability

The International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) addresses the dependability concept through the Technical Committee TC 56, which develops and maintains international standards. These standards provide systematic methods and tools for assessing and managing the dependability of equipment, services, and systems throughout their life cycles. Based on the vocabulary provided by IEC in this paper, edge AI dependability is defined as the ability of the edge AI system to perform as and when required, operate as desired, and satisfy the defined functional and non-functional requirements. The term edge AI system dependability includes the core system's attributes and characteristics such as availability, connectability, maintainability, privacy, reliability, resilience, safety, security, to which AI specific attributes and characteristics are added, e.g., accountability, accuracy, authenticity, credibility, controllability, compliance, durability, efficiency, explainability, fairness, inclusiveness, integrity, interpretability, interoperability, learnability, performance, robustness, transparency, understandability, usability.

The attributes and characteristics of edge AI system dependability can be expressed qualitatively or quantitatively through expressing the ability to perform by defining the functional and non-

functional requirements in terms of features, functions and qualities to be performed, when the performance is to be achieved, considering operational conditions, the KPIs and measures specified.

Following the concept in [1][3] a systematic structure of the concepts of edge AI dependability consists of three elements: attributes, threats, and means.

The attributes or characteristics are represented by the ways to assess the dependability of an edge AI system (availability, connectability, maintainability, privacy, reliability, resilience, safety, security, etc.). The attributes or characteristics are qualities of an edge AI system. These can be assessed to determine its overall dependability by defined KPIs using qualitative or quantitative measures.

The threats are represented by the elements that can affect the dependability of an edge AI system (errors, failures, faults). An error is a discrepancy between an edge AI system's intended behaviour and actual behaviour inside the edge AI system boundary. Errors occur at runtime when some part of the edge AI system enters an unexpected state due to the activation of a fault. Errors are generated from invalid states and algorithms and are challenging to find without unique mechanisms. A failure is an instance in time when an edge AI system displays behaviour that is errant from its specification. An error may not necessarily cause a failure, but the edge AI system's performance is influenced. A fault is a defect in an edge AI system and its presence may or may not lead to a failure due to input and state conditions that may never cause the fault to be executed so that an error occurs.

The means are represented by the ways to increase an edge AI system's dependability (forecasting, prevention, removal, tolerance) and are intended to reduce the number of failures made visible to the users of an edge AI system.

2.1.9. Edge AI System Trustworthiness

Trustworthy edge AI systems are essential for user confidence, the safe deployment of edge AI technologies including generative AI, and ensuring that these systems enhance technological, economic and societal progress.

The Dictionary.com defines "trustworthiness" as the quality of being deserving of trust or confidence, dependability. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) [16] defines "trustworthiness" as the following: "trustworthiness is the demonstrable likelihood that the system performs according to designed behaviour under any set of conditions as evidenced by characteristics including, but not limited to, safety, security, privacy, reliability and resilience. In computer security, a chain of trust is established by validating each component of hardware and software from the bottom up. It is intended to ensure that only trusted software and hardware can be used while still retaining some level of flexibility".

Based on the definition of trustworthiness in ISO/IEC TS 5723:2022, edge AI trustworthiness can be defined as the ability of the edge AI system to meet the functional and non-functional requirements and user expectations in a verifiable way, which includes measurability and demonstrability by means of objective evidence that needs verification to ensure that user expectations are met. The verification process considers the definition of KPIs, measures, monitoring, ongoing assessment, transparency, and alignment with societal values and needs.

ISO/IEC TS 5723:2022 highlights that trustworthiness characteristics include accountability, accuracy, authenticity, availability, controllability, integrity, quality, reliability, privacy, resilience, robustness, safety, security, transparency, and usability.

Trustworthiness is an attribute that can be applied to edge AI systems and related services, products, technology, data and information.

ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020 surveys topics related to trustworthiness in AI systems, including approaches to establish trust in AI systems through transparency, explainability, controllability, etc.; engineering pitfalls and typical associated threats and risks to AI systems, along with possible mitigation techniques and methods; and approaches to assess and achieve availability, resiliency, reliability, accuracy, safety, security and privacy of AI systems that can be applied as well to edge AI systems. The specification of levels of trustworthiness for AI systems is out of the scope of the document.

2.2. AI and Edge AI Taxonomy

Presenting a taxonomy and classification of edge AI systems is essential for understanding the landscape of edge deployments and defining such systems' functional and non-functional requirements. These classifications guide hardware, software, edge AI technology stack and data sets design and inform the strategic deployment of edge AI solutions across various industry domains. This helps maximise the potential of AI at the edge while addressing specific challenges and requirements of localised processing.

Creating a taxonomy and classification for edge AI systems involves categorising these systems based on various dimensions, including the specific AI domain areas they serve. In this deliverable, the edge AI domain areas defined are as following:

Computer Vision: Edge AI domain that processes visual information from cameras, sensors, or stored on device at the edge, enabling applications like facial recognition, object detection, and video analytics.

Machine Vision: Branch of engineering that designs and implements systems that allow machines to interpret visual information locally on the device. Machine Vision systems include optical sensors, hardware, algorithms, data storage and processing. Enables instant analysis and action based on visual input, which is essential for applications like autonomous vehicles, quality inspection in manufacturing, and live security monitoring.

Speech Systems: Edge AI domain that addresses the deployment of speech recognition, processing, and generation technologies using AI directly on edge audio devices. The approach facilitates real-time processing and analysis of audio data at the point of capture, leveraging the benefits of edge computing.

Natural Language Processing (NLP): Edge AI domain that handles human language data for applications such as voice recognition, language translation, and sentiment analysis on edge devices. NLP is defined in [18] as system information processing based upon natural language understanding defined in ISO/IEC 2382:2015 as natural language comprehension extraction of information, by a functional unit, from text or speech communicated to it in a natural language, and

the production of a description for both the given text or speech and what it represents or natural language generation defined as a task of converting data carrying semantics into natural language.

Predictive Analytics: Edge AI domain that utilises historical data to forecast future outcomes and provide predictive maintenance and anomaly detection.

Robotics and Control Systems: Edge AI domain that implements real-time AI-driven decision-making for robotic movements and industrial automation.

Machine Learning: Edge AI domain that addresses the deployment of ML models optimised to fit edge devices limited computational power, memory, and energy constraints. To maintain performance, this involves model compression techniques like quantisation, pruning, and distillation. ML is defined in [18] as the process of optimising model parameters through computational techniques, such that the model's behaviour reflects the data or experience.

Deep Learning: An edge AI domain that involves deploying deep learning models on edge devices. DL, a subset of ML, utilises neural networks with multiple layers (deep neural networks) to model complex patterns and representations in data. DL models perform inference directly on edge devices, enabling real-time data processing and decision-making. DL is an approach to creating rich hierarchical representations by training neural networks with many hidden layers. This process allows the neural network to refine the final output progressively. DL can reduce or eliminate the need for feature engineering, as the most relevant features are identified automatically. However, DL can require significant time and computing resources [18].

Supervised Learning: Edge AI domain that focuses on implementing supervised learning techniques directly on edge devices. Supervised learning is a type of ML where models are trained on labelled datasets, meaning the input data is paired with the correct output. This training enables models to make predictions or decisions when encountering new, unlabelled data. Supervised learning is defined in [18] and [20] as "machine learning that makes use of labelled data during training". In this context, ML models are trained with training data that include a known or determined output or target variable (the label). The value of the target variable for a given sample is also known as the ground truth. Depending on the task, labels can be of any type, including categorical, binary, or numeric values or structured objects (e.g., sequences, images, trees, or graphs). Labels can be part of the original dataset, but in many cases, they are determined manually or through other processes. Supervised learning can be used for classification and regression tasks and more complex tasks pertaining to structured prediction.

[18]**Unsupervised Learning:** Edge AI domain that focuses on implementing unsupervised learning techniques directly on edge devices. Unsupervised learning is a type of ML used to infer patterns from unlabelled data, where the edge AI system tries to learn the underlying structure without explicit output guidance. These systems can adapt to input data in real time, updating models as they encounter new patterns. Unsupervised ML is defined in [18] [20] as "machine learning that makes use of unlabelled data during training". Unsupervised ML can be useful in cases such as clustering, where the objective is to determine points of commonality among the samples in the input data. Reducing the dimensionality of a training dataset is another application of unsupervised

machine learning, where the most statistically relevant features are determined irrespective of any label.

Semi-supervised Learning: Edge AI domain that focuses on implementing semi-supervised learning techniques directly on edge devices. Semi-supervised ML is defined as "machine learning that makes use of both labelled and unlabelled data during training." It is a hybrid of supervised and unsupervised machine learning [18]. Semi-supervised machine learning is helpful in cases where labelling all the samples in an extensive training dataset would be prohibitive from a time or cost perspective.

Reinforcement Learning: Edge AI domain that uses AI models to improve decision-making through trial and error, relevant in dynamic environments like autonomous vehicles or drones. Reinforcement learning is the process of training an agent(s) interacting with its environment to achieve a predefined goal [18]. In reinforcement learning, a machine learning agent(s) learns through an iterative process of trial and error. The goal of agent(s) is to find the strategy (i.e. build a model) for obtaining the best rewards from the environment. For each trial (successful or not), the environment provides indirect feedback. Based on this feedback, the agent(s) then adjust its behaviour (i.e., its model) [18].

First Principles: Edge AI domain that arises from the fundamental properties and behaviours of persisting physical systems, such as energy, entropy, and the ability to maintain and propagate information over time. By deducing intelligence from these first principles, we understand it as the optimization of actions and decisions that align with the natural laws governing the system's environment and as an emergent capacity of a system to process information, adapt, and achieve goals within the constraints of a physical universe [56].

Distributed ML Learning: Execution of training and inference processes across multiple machines. Parallelization can be applied to datasets and models [85][86]. In dataset parallelism, each node computes gradients and local statistics on a subset of the original dataset. The resulting updates are subsequently aggregated by a parameter server. In model parallelism, each node trains a specific part of the model, with the central server coordinating the integration of the different components. By combining the two approaches, distributed machine learning facilitates the training of complex models on large datasets that would be infeasible on a single machine.

Federated Learning: Federated learning is a decentralized machine learning approach where multiple devices collaboratively train a model, while each seeing only part of the data. Instead of sending data to a central server, each device trains the model locally using only its own data. The results are then sent to a central server, where they are aggregated to improve the global model. The rationales for federated learning often have to do with privacy and/or certainty.

Transfer learning: Refers to a series of methods where data intended for solving one problem is leveraged to apply the knowledge gained from it to a different problem [18]. For example, information gained from recognising house numbers in a street view can be used to recognise handwritten numbers.

Continuous learning: Edge AI domain used for continuous AI models training. It is also known as continual learning or lifelong learning, is incremental training of a model that takes place continuously while the system is running in production. This is a particular case of retraining, where model updates are repeated, occur with high frequency, and do not involve any interruption of operation [18]. In many AI systems, the system is trained during the development process before it is put into production. This is like standard software development, where the system is built and tested fully before it is put into production. The behaviour of such systems is assessed during the verification process and is expected to be unchanged during the operation phase. AI systems that embody continuous learning involve the incremental update of the model in the system as it operates during production. The data input to the system during operation is analysed to produce an output from the system and simultaneously used to adjust the model in the system, to improve the model based on the production data. Continuous learning can help overcome the limitations of the original training data, as well as data and concept drift. However, it also presents significant challenges in ensuring that the AI system still operates correctly as it learns.

On-device training: Training a model directly on an edge device, like mobile phones, embedded systems, gaming consoles, web browsers, and more. This approach differs from training on a centralized server or cloud infrastructure. On-device training is particularly valuable when data privacy is paramount and sharing it with external servers or clouds is not feasible. Additionally, it is advantageous for personalization tasks, as the model can be tailored and trained directly on the user's device. Existing on-device training approaches and solutions cover: (i) last-layer or bias-only backpropagation; (ii) sparse backpropagation; (iii) complete backpropagation for fine-tuning; and (iv) complete backpropagation with optimized memory consumption.

Training data: Consists of data samples used to train an ML algorithm. Typically, the data samples relate to some topic of concern and can consist of structured or unstructured data, either unlabelled or labelled. In the latter case, the label guides the machine learning model's training process [18].

Trained model: A trained model is the result of model training, which, in turn, is defined as the process of establishing or improving the parameters of a machine learning model based on a machine learning algorithm by using training data [18]. An ML model is a mathematical construct that generates an inference or prediction based on input data or information. An AI system should use the trained model to make predictions based on production data from the area of interest. Various standardised formats exist to store and transmit the trained model as a set of numbers.

Planning Optimisation and Scheduling Systems: An edge AI domain that focuses on deploying sophisticated algorithms to manage and optimise tasks, resources, and processes in real-time directly on edge devices. These systems aim to enhance operational efficiency, improve decision-making, and enable autonomous functionality in various settings, from industrial automation to smart home management.

2.3. Edge AI System Elements

The development of edge AI solutions leads to the emergence of multimodal edge AI implementations that yield real-time performance at the edge for various industrial sectors. These

require the integration of edge AI hardware, software, AI technology stack building blocks and data in an edge AI design framework for the whole system, as illustrated in Figure 2-2.

Figure 2-2: Edge AI system components.

Defining the non-functional and functional requirements, aligned with quality properties, supports to address holistically all the edge AI system components including hardware, software, AI techniques/methods and data and treat edge AI systems as a set of systems and system elements that interact to provide a unique intelligent capabilities that none of the constituent systems can accomplish on its own facilitating interaction of the constituent systems in this system of systems concept.

Developing a conceptual framework for edge AI system of systems design and implementation is critical to be used as a reference for defining the functional and non-functional requirements of edge AI systems across the computing continuum and various industrial applications.

2.3.1. Edge AI Technology Stack

Edge AI technology encompasses a multi-layered approach that facilitates the deployment of AI capabilities directly at the edge. This architecture allows for efficient data processing, analysis, and decision-making closer to where data is generated, significantly reducing latency and bandwidth usage. A five-layer edge AI technology stack is presented in Figure 2-3 [48].

Edge AI hardware is the foundational layer, which contains at least three components reflecting the processing units responsible for performing specialised AI operations. The neuromorphic hardware components consist of new ultra-low-power silicon chip architectures (e.g., neuromorphic modules and chips, digital, analogue, spike NN) incorporating different chip designs and algorithms to mimic how the human brain works. The accelerator set of components consists of silicon chips designed to perform highly parallel functions and accelerate AI workloads required during training and

inference, such as GPUs, NPUs, VPUs, TPUs, FPGAs, or ASICs. The HW layer includes in-memory computing architectures to support high-speed data processing within the chip, essential for handling real-time AI applications. Energy efficiency is critical for HW designs that enable AI calculations on remote edge devices without excessive energy consumption.

Figure 2-3: Edge AI technology stack layers. [48]

Edge AI interfaces layer covers the mechanisms through which edge devices communicate with each other and with other parts of the system, ensuring seamless data exchange and control. The head node components coordinate computations among accelerators and provides interfaces for developers to integrate AI functionalities into devices and applications. Interfaces can include technology for preprocessing data locally.

Edge AI platforms provide the infrastructure for deploying and managing AI models on edge devices, incorporating tools for model development, optimisation, deployment, and monitoring. The platforms layer is used for AI and ML/DL deployment and consists of three sublayers, which aim to abstract firmware from the underlying hardware. The framework sublayer comprises packages that trigger AI frameworks, such as TensorFlow, TensorFlow Lite, Caffe, PyTorch, Theano, etc., via the interface layer, which connects the hardware and platform layers and facilitates communication. The algorithms sublayer consists of rules to achieve optimal inference according to the training method employed, such as backpropagation, evolutionary, and contrasted divergence. The architectures sublayer consists of many continuously evolving neural network architectures, such as CNN, RNN, etc.

The edge AI learning/training layer involves the methods and processes used to train AI models specifically for edge device deployment, emphasising the need for lightweight, adaptable models.

The layer consists of two sublayers. The methods sublayer involves techniques for optimising the model for specific domain data, such as supervised, unsupervised, reinforcement, and first-principles learning. Techniques like pruning, quantisation, and knowledge distillation aimed at reducing model complexity and size while maintaining accuracy are part of this sublayer. Different learning approaches, such as federated learning, are included, where models are trained across numerous decentralised devices without sharing raw data, enhancing privacy and reducing the need for data transfer. The data type sublayer consists of categories of domain input data, such as labelled and unlabelled data.

The edge AI applications and services layer consists of end-user applications and services that leverage AI at the edge to deliver value and insights. Solutions can be customised based on generic data or customer-specific training data. The AI technology stack provides a common understanding of the AI layers and components when implementing and benchmarking various AI technologies and applications.

By integrating these layers, edge AI technology delivers intelligent solutions directly at the data generation and use site. This layered approach facilitates the development of edge AI applications tailored for specific tasks and the enhancement of existing systems with real-time learning, adaptability, and efficiency.

2.3.2. Hardware

Edge AI hardware refers to the computing devices designed to perform AI computations directly at the edge of networks, near the source of data generation across the micro-, deep- and meta-edge continuum. The primary goal of edge AI hardware is to enable real-time data processing, reduce latency, and enhance privacy by optimising and reducing data transmission.

Edge AI systems can run on various hardware platforms and take different forms, from central processing units (CPUs), and microcontroller units (MCUs) to advanced neural processing units (NPU). The edge AI hardware is designed as compact system on a chips (SoCs), system on modules (SoMs), and Application-Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs) that consume minimal power, making it suitable for deployment in mobile, portable, or remote edge devices.

An ASIC is an integrated circuit customised for a particular use. ASICs are an option for providing AI-specific functionality. An ASIC can be customised as an accelerator to speed up the AI process by offering functions such as dedicated parallel multiplying-accumulating blocks, optimised memory allocation and lower precision arithmetic. ASICs provide a higher computational capability for AI with lower spatial volumes, cost and energy consumption. ASICs enable AI to be implemented in space- and power-constrained edge IoT devices [18].

An SoC is an integrated circuit integrating on a single substrate/chip or microchip multiple cores, including a mix of CPUs, GPUs, TPUs, and other types of functional units, e.g., digital signal processors (DSPs), neural processing units (NPU), image signal processors, (ISPs), memory, input/output ports, secondary storage, and sometimes Wi-Fi and cellular modems. SoC organisation enhances performance and reduces energy consumption and semiconductor die area compared with motherboard-based architecture with equivalent functionality but discrete components.

An SoM is a board-level circuit that integrates an embedded processing system function in a single module that includes microprocessor cores, SoCs, memory blocks, communication interfaces, and hardware peripherals on a single production-ready substrate. SoMs offer a flexible and modular approach to system design.

The edge AI HW includes specialised processing units, such as AI accelerators implemented as GPUs (Graphics Processing Units), TPUs (Tensor Processing Units), NPUs, Vision Processing Units (VPUs) and neuromorphic units, that are optimised for the parallel processing requirements of AI workloads. Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) and ASICs are also used to deliver high efficiency for specific AI tasks, providing customisable solutions tailored to various applications.

Increased performance edge AI HW is necessary to deal with the aggregation of multiple endpoints, multimodality of data and cross-inference from many sources. This increased functionality and breadth of scope also increases the consequence of faults, so the requirements for security and reliable operation also increase as one moves away from the micro-edge. New edge processing circuits and devices with novel processing architectures are emerging for edge AI implementations, including integrating several accelerators and processing units (CPUs, GPUs, TPUs, NPUs, ISPs, VPUs) into one chip or SoM circuit.

Edge AI implementations require low-power AI accelerator architectures (e.g., VPU, GPU, TPU) suitable for edge devices and the given application use case. They must also establish an appropriate deployment platform, learning frameworks (e.g., TensorFlow, PyTorch, TensorFlow Lite, ONNXruntime, TensorRT) that meets the required needs and a robust programming language (Python, C++) suitable for edge AI development and the platform/framework.

Edge AI hardware is equipped with the necessary computational power to run inference tasks locally, allowing devices to make predictions and decisions in real-time based on new data inputs. The HW supports various connectivity options, such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and cellular networks, to communicate efficiently with other devices and systems. Deep- and meta-edge AI hardware can have the necessary computational power to partially and fully train AI models.

The HW provides the computational power necessary for real-time data analysis and decision-making based on AI algorithms and is optimised to reduce latency and increase bandwidth efficiency, which is critical for real-time applications. The HW facilitates easier scaling of AI applications, as deploying additional edge devices can enhance overall processing without overwhelming centralised resources.

As computing performance increases, edge AI hardware is advancing to enable the local processing of more complex AI models and larger datasets. This is driven by chip design and architecture innovations that optimise performance and energy consumption.

2.3.3. Software

Edge AI software and platforms provide the tools and frameworks to develop, deploy, and manage AI models directly on edge devices. These solutions effectively harness edge hardware's computational power, offering flexibility and efficiency in implementing AI applications across various environments.

Edge AI software platforms often include tools for model optimisation, such as pruning, quantisation, and knowledge distillation. These techniques reduce the size of AI models and improve their performance on resource-constrained devices without significantly compromising accuracy.

Edge AI software supports AI frameworks like TensorFlow, PyTorch, Keras, ONNX, and Caffe, enabling developers to use familiar tools and libraries while ensuring models can be executed efficiently on edge devices.

Software Development Kits (SDKs) and Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) are tailored for edge environments, simplifying integrating AI capabilities into applications.

Edge AI software can be categorised into various types based on functionality and use cases. Some common categories of edge AI software include:

- **Machine and Deep Learning Frameworks:** These libraries and tools allow developers to build, train, and deploy machine learning models.
- **Natural Language Processing (NLP) Software:** NLP software enables machines to understand, interpret, and generate human language.
- **Computer and Machine Vision Software:** These tools focus on image and video analysis, enabling AI systems to understand and interpret visual data.
- **Speech Recognition and Synthesis Software:** This category includes software that can transcribe spoken language into text and generate speech from written text.
- **Edge AI Chatbots and Virtual Assistants:** These applications use natural language processing and machine learning to interact with users and provide relevant information or services.
- **Reinforcement Learning Frameworks:** These tools are designed to develop edge AI systems that learn through trial and error, often used in robotics and autonomous applications.
- **Active inference frameworks:** These tools allow to formulate agents with adaptive behaviour to the deployment scenario, which inherits from the physics of self-organization, i.e., first-principles. These tools enable maximizing (Bayesian) model evidence, via inference, learning, and model selection.
- **Edge AI Development Platforms:** These platforms offer end-to-end solutions for building, training, and deploying AI models, often with pre-built models and drag-and-drop interfaces.
- **Edge AI Data Annotation Tools:** These tools help label and annotate data to train edge AI models.
- **Edge AI-based Business Solutions:** These are edge AI applications designed to solve specific business problems.

Edge AI platforms often support deployment across heterogeneous devices, ensuring that AI models work cohesively within diverse hardware ecosystems.

Edge AI software and platforms support edge AI system developers in creating robust, scalable, and efficient AI solutions that leverage the full potential of edge computing. By focusing on optimisation, compatibility, and ease of deployment, these tools make it possible to meet the varied demands of real-world applications that require speed, reliability, and autonomy.

Example of Edge AI software platforms:

ST Edge AI Suite: This suite offers a set of tools and software solutions to simplify the development and deployment of AI applications on edge devices, particularly those powered by STM's microcontrollers and microprocessors. The suite caters to developers looking to implement AI capabilities such as machine learning and neural network inference directly on low-power, resource-constrained devices.

eIQ® Auto Machine Learning (ML) Toolkit: Offers a suite of tools aimed at simplifying and accelerating the deployment of machine learning models on edge devices, particularly within the automotive sector. This toolkit is part of NXP's broader eIQ Machine Learning Software Development Environment, designed to cater to various ML applications across diverse hardware platforms offered by NXP.

Google Coral: Provides the Edge TPU with an SDK for accelerating ML inferencing at the edge, supporting TensorFlow Lite models.

NVIDIA Jetson: Offers a comprehensive platform with SDKs like JetPack and deep learning tools that support high-performance AI applications.

Azure IoT Edge: Microsoft's platform for deploying AI workloads on the edge, integrated with Azure cloud services for a seamless hybrid solution.

AWS Greengrass: Facilitates the execution of local computing, messaging, and machine learning inference capabilities on connected devices.

OpenVINO Toolkit: Developed by Intel, optimises AI model performance on Intel hardware across CPUs, VPUs, FPGAs, and integrated GPUs.

2.3.4. Edge AI Frameworks, Methods, and Techniques

Edge AI frameworks are software libraries and tools designed to simplify and facilitate the deployment, development, and optimisation of edge AI models on edge devices. These frameworks address the unique challenges and requirements of edge computing, where resources such as processing power, memory, and energy are often constrained.

Edge AI frameworks enable the deployment of pre-trained AI models on various edge devices, ensuring they perform efficiently in resource-constrained environments by using techniques like quantisation, pruning, and sparsification to reduce the size and computational requirements of AI models, making them suitable for edge conditions, ensure compatibility with machine learning libraries and frameworks like TensorFlow, PyTorch, and ONNX, allowing developers to leverage existing models and facilitate efficient data preprocessing and handling on edge devices to support real-time analytics and decision-making.

The edge AI frameworks support multiple AI models, including deep learning neural networks, machine learning algorithms, and computer vision models. They are designed with a small footprint to operate effectively on devices with limited resources without compromising performance.

TensorFlow Lite: An extension of TensorFlow designed to run machine learning models on mobile and edge devices. It supports model optimisation through quantisation and provides an interpreter capable of running efficiently on various types of hardware accelerators.

ONNX Runtime: An open-source inference engine focused on providing performance-enhanced runtime options for models expressed in the ONNX format. It provides extensive hardware compatibility, supporting CPU, GPU, and custom accelerators.

Apache MXNet: A flexible and efficient deep learning framework supported by open source. With its Gluon API, MXNet is efficient for training and deploying models on edge devices in real time.

NVIDIA TensorRT: A high-performance deep learning inference library specifically for NVIDIA GPUs and designed to accelerate inference for deep learning models.

OpenVINO Toolkit: Developed by Intel, it optimises and deploys AI inference across Intel architectures, including CPUs, integrated GPUs, and FPGAs, primarily for vision applications.

Arm NN: Provides an inference engine optimised for Arm Cortex CPUs and GPUs, enabling efficient execution of neural networks on edge devices.

2.3.5. Data

Data plays a multifaceted role in edge AI systems, serving as the foundation upon which these systems operate and derive insights. The characteristics and handling of data significantly influence the performance, reliability, and efficiency of edge AI applications.

Several challenges relate to data in edge AI, among them data quality, volume, and integration. Data quality ensures that the data used for training and inference is accurate and representative of real-world conditions, which is vital for model reliability. Data volume requires handling volumes of data generated by numerous devices to match edge devices' processing power and storage capacity. Integrating data from diverse sources and formats is complex in heterogeneous environments with different types of devices and sensors requiring new multi-modality techniques and algorithms.

Data is driving the ability of edge AI systems to learn, adapt, and make informed decisions quickly and efficiently. As edge AI continues to evolve, strategies to optimise data usage focus on quality, security, and efficient processing.

The datasets used in edge AI applications span various domains and can differ based on the application and field for which the edge AI model is being developed. Several categories of edge AI datasets based on their applications are presented below:

Anomaly Detection Datasets are designed to train edge AI models to identify anomalies or outliers in various types of data, such as electrical signals, network traffic, industrial machinery, motors, or the behaviour of edge devices.

Audio and Speech Datasets encompass audio recordings paired with corresponding transcriptions or labels. These datasets are essential for developing edge AI models for speech recognition, keyword spotting, speaker identification, and other audio-related tasks.

Environmental Datasets consist of data collected from sensors that monitor environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, and air quality. These datasets are utilised for applications in environmental monitoring and sustainability.

Gesture and Motion Datasets involve data captured from sensors like accelerometers and gyroscopes to recognise human gestures or movements. These datasets are used in gesture and human activity recognition applications.

Healthcare Datasets focus on applications related to healthcare, including medical image analysis, disease diagnosis, and patient monitoring.

Image Classification Datasets consist of images labelled with corresponding class identifiers. These datasets are used to train and evaluate edge AI models for tasks such as object recognition and scene classification.

Natural Language Processing (NLP) Datasets for edge AI models contain text data and corresponding labels or annotations. These datasets are applied in text classification, sentiment analysis, and named entity recognition tasks.

Object Detection Datasets feature images annotated with bounding boxes around objects of interest. These datasets are essential for training edge AI models to detect and localise one or multiple objects within an image. Object detection is a critical technique in computer vision that involves identifying relevant objects in images and video frames. The algorithms used for object detection employ advanced machine learning and deep learning architectures to analyse image data and recognise and pinpoint objects of interest. The output typically includes the object's name and a bounding box indicating its location. Deep learning architectures for object detection include Single Shot Detector (SSD), You Only Look Once (YOLO), and Region-based Convolutional Neural Networks (R-CNN), among others.

Semantic Segmentation Datasets provide pixel-level annotations for each image, indicating the class to which each pixel belongs. These datasets are utilised for tasks like image segmentation and instance segmentation.

Time Series Datasets are employed across edge AI applications, including IoT sensor data, equipment health monitoring, predictive maintenance, and forecasting. These datasets contain sequential data points, including timestamps and associated target values.

3. Edge AI System Engineering

Edge AI system engineering is a holistic and interdisciplinary approach to designing, developing, and managing edge AI systems. It involves applying principles, methods, and tools to define, analyse, and validate system requirements and specifications.

3.1.1. Systems Engineering

Systems engineering is a systematic, interdisciplinary approach to a system's design, implementation, technical management, operation, and eventual retirement. A "system" is an integrated assembly of elements that collectively deliver the capability necessary to fulfil a specific need. These elements encompass all hardware, software, equipment, facilities, personnel,

processes, and procedures required to achieve the desired system-level outcomes. The outcomes include system-level qualities, properties, characteristics, functions, behaviours, and performance metrics. The unique value of the system, beyond the sum of its parts and components, is primarily derived from the interrelationships and interactions among these parts, emphasising the importance of their integration. This holistic perspective is crucial when making technical decisions, ensuring that stakeholder requirements for functional, physical, and operational performance are met within the intended use environment throughout the system's lifecycle, all while adhering to constraints related to cost, schedule, and other factors. Systems engineering thus serves as a disciplined methodology that helps manage and contain the life cycle costs of a system, embodying a logical and structured way of thinking.

Systems engineering focuses on developing an operable system that meets specified requirements within often conflicting constraints. It is a holistic, integrative discipline where the contributions of various engineering specialities, such as electrical engineering, software engineering, power engineering, and human factors engineering, are evaluated and balanced against one another to create a cohesive whole. This approach ensures that no single discipline's perspective dominates the system design.

The system's engineering aims to achieve a safe and balanced design amidst competing interests and multiple, sometimes conflicting constraints. Throughout the process, continuous validation is essential to confirm that the system's operational goals are being met. This balanced and integrative approach ensures that the final system is robust, efficient, and capable of fulfilling its intended purpose.

3.1.2. Requirements Engineering

Requirement engineering is the process of formalising and defining needs at each stage of system design, including customer requirements, design requirements, and testing requirements. It focuses on identifying, tracing, and characterising these needs to ensure their implementation and impact are clearly understood and deals with developing and verifying the system requirements.

Requirements engineering is an addition to systems engineering and focuses on an essential concept in implementing systems engineering: practices related to the process (e.g., quality, standards to be applied) or product development (e.g., non-functional, functional requirements).

Requirements engineering is the discipline of establishing user requirements and specifying hardware, software, AI, and data systems. Defining requirements involves determining what users want from a system and understanding what the needs mean regarding design. It is closely related to hardware, software, AI, and data engineering and focuses on designing and developing the system that users want.

Following good requirements engineering practices helps achieve the primary objective of ensuring that the delivered system meets the customer's needs. Requirements engineering consists of establishing and documenting requirements. The various activities associated with requirements engineering are formulation, elicitation, specification, analysis, verification and validation, and

management. Requirements formulation involves collecting, organising, communicating, and managing requirements.

Several standards focus on requirements engineering. One example is ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018, which addresses requirements engineering and specifies the required processes implemented in the engineering activities that result in requirements for systems and software products (including services) throughout the life cycle.

Requirements engineering is the discipline of establishing user requirements and specifying hardware, software, AI, and data systems. Defining requirements involves determining what users want from a system and understanding what the needs mean regarding design. It is closely related to hardware, software, AI, and data engineering and focuses on designing and developing the system that users want.

4. Edge AI Non-Functional Requirements

4.1. Definition

The field of edge AI is relatively new and there is no established standardised definition solely for edge AI system non-functional requirements (NFRs) provided by ISO or IEEE standards. This paper intends to use the concepts associated with NFRs for edge AI systems using broader concepts of systems based on the existing hardware, software, AI components and data engineering. These concepts guide specifying non-functional requirements that can be adapted to edge AI environments' unique characteristics and constraints.

While no standard exclusively defines edge AI non-functional requirements, ISO and IEEE standards such as IEEE 29148:2018, IEEE 2874, and ISO/IEC 25010:2011 provide robust frameworks for understanding and specifying these requirements. Non-functional requirements are essential for ensuring that a system performs correctly and meets broader quality and operational demands, aligning with stakeholder expectations and regulatory constraints.

Edge AI system non-functional requirements (NFRs) refer to the criteria describing how a system operates rather than specific behaviours or functions. These requirements define an edge AI system's quality attributes and characteristics, performance benchmarks, and constraints, encompassing functional suitability, spatiability, reliability, performance efficiency, usability, security, compatibility, scalability, maintainability, and portability.

Capturing non-functional requirements is critical to ensuring edge AI systems meet necessary quality and performance standards. Non-functional requirements in this context focus on "how" an edge AI system performs its functions, providing detailed specifications for quality attributes.

4.2. Methodology for defining NFRs.

The NFRs can be mapped to the ISO/IEC 25010:2023 [24] attributes or characteristics and sub-characteristics for edge AI systems and data quality requirements in ISO/IEC 25012:2008 [25].

A summary of the product quality model characteristics presented in ISO/IEC 25010:2023 is illustrated in Figure 4-1.

Each NFR has a KPI identified and a measure to provide a verifiable and quantifiable (qualitative/quantitative) assessment. The methodology proposed is based on the measures described in ISO/IEC 25023:2016 and ISO/IEC 25021:2012 (parts of the ISO/IEC 25000 SQuaRE series - System and software quality requirements and evaluation) as reference.

The ISO/IEC 25012 standard can be used in edge AI systems to extend the product quality model defined in ISO 25010 with the data properties. The standard covers data held in a structured format, and it specifies a general data quality model. The target is data processed or stored by the system which can be considered persistent data. Conformance of data to a data design specification is outside the scope of the standard. Data quality is the degree to which data properties satisfy explicit and implicit needs when used in a specified context. The quality is intended to be application-dependent. It does not consider universal data quality that can be applied for any purpose.

SOFTWARE PRODUCT QUALITY								
FUNCTIONAL SUITABILITY	PERFORMANCE EFFICIENCY	COMPATIBILITY	INTERACTION CAPABILITY	RELIABILITY	SECURITY	MAINTAINABILITY	FLEXIBILITY	SAFETY
FUNCTIONAL COMPLETENESS	TIME BEHAVIOUR	CO-EXISTENCE	APPROPRIATENESS RECOGNIZABILITY	FAULTLESSNESS	CONFIDENTIALITY	MODULARITY	ADAPTABILITY	OPERATIONAL CONSTRAINT
FUNCTIONAL CORRECTNESS	RESOURCE UTILIZATION	INTEROPERABILITY	LEARNABILITY	AVAILABILITY	INTEGRITY	REUSABILITY	SCALABILITY	RISK IDENTIFICATION
FUNCTIONAL APPROPRIATENESS	CAPACITY		OPERABILITY	FAULT TOLERANCE	NON-REPUDIATION	ANALYSABILITY	INSTALLABILITY	FAIL SAFE
			USER ERROR PROTECTION	RECOVERABILITY	ACCOUNTABILITY	MODIFIABILITY	REPLACEABILITY	HAZARD WARNING
			USER ENGAGEMENT		AUTHENTICITY	TESTABILITY		SAFE INTEGRATION
			INCLUSIVITY		RESISTANCE			
			USER ASSISTANCE					
			SELF-DESCRIPTIVENESS					

Figure 4-1: ISO/IEC 25010 overview, including characteristics and sub-characteristics

Data quality characteristics are defined as the attributes that affect quality. ISO/IEC 25012 defines data quality through two main categories: inherent data quality and system-dependent data quality. these categories encompass fifteen data quality characteristics, five for inherent data quality (accuracy, completeness, consistency, credibility, currentness and ten for system-dependent data quality (accessibility, compliance, confidentiality, efficiency, precision, traceability, understandability, availability, portability, recoverability).

The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems [57] highlighted in 2016 the importance of integrating socio-technical standards early in development to ensure that autonomous and intelligent systems align with human values, intentions, and understanding, thereby reducing the risk of unwanted behaviours. These standards are informed by IEEE’s Ethically-Aligned Design P7000 Series of standards that address human rights, well-being, accountability, and transparency for AI and autonomous intelligent systems.

In response to this initiative, the Spatial Web Foundation [58] and the IEEE P2874 Spatial Web, Architecture, and Governance Working Group [59] have developed the IEEE P2874 standards, including the Spatial Web Protocol, Architecture, and Governance specifications. These specifications define the system requirements for the interoperability and governance of cyber-physical systems, encompassing autonomous devices, applications, spatial content, and operations. Networked communication systems designed to meet these specifications enable the universal

representation of all statements and interactions in the physical and socially-constructed world, making them suitable for computational modelling, simulation, and automation. The IEEE approved these specifications in July 2024, which will be available shortly.

The design and development of edge AI systems need to embed AI trustworthiness concepts. These encompass several aspects addressed by system engineering dependability that include several system quality properties (e.g., security, safety, availability, connectability, resilience, reliability, maintainability, and privacy) covered by ISO/IEC TS 5723:2022 in addition to ISO/IEC 25010:2023 and ISO/IEC 25012:2008.

The further development of edge AI systems includes ethical edge AI considerations (e.g., fairness, responsibility, accountability, governance) and specific (e.g., explainability, interpretability) that are intrinsic to the data-centric and black-box nature of ML/DL edge AI.

Using the information provided in [24] non-functional requirements for edge AI systems are specifying how well the functionality should present itself and behave, aligning to the other quality characteristics outlined in ISO/IEC 25010 System and software quality models, ISO/IEC 25012 Data quality model and specific AI quality attributes or characteristics. Non-functional requirements are related to some, or all the functionality and typically functional requirements are associated with appropriate non-functional requirements, either individually or in groups.

The non-functional requirements for edge AI systems can have a two-layer representation following the ISO/IEC 25010 model with a "high-level" non-functional requirement assigned to the quality characteristics or attributes and a "low-level" non-functional requirement assigned to the quality sub-characteristics or attributes.

4.3. Edge AI non-functional requirements, key KPIs and measures.

The following section provides examples structured in tables of edge AI non-functional requirements, key KPIs, and measures that researchers and practitioners can use as references for their projects.

NFR aspect	NFR description
Domain example	Digital industry domain.
Name	Characteristic: Compatibility Sub-characteristics: Interoperability
Definition	Interoperability of the SSMA - method(s). What are the constrains where all systems competing for, internally and externally.
Description	Degree to which two or more decision making systems, products or components can exchange information/knowledge and use the information/knowledge that has been exchanged.
What is measured:	Number of downstream systems that leverage the results of these models. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Response time for inference on downstream system. • Generalization of the model results. flexibility of the deployment environment (e.g., different frameworks – Keras, TensorFlow, etc.)
KPI	Number of use cases which the model results can be used for. Number of different deployment environment which the model can be host in.

Methods of collection/ measurement and verification/ validation	Develop testing framework to measure inference response time on downstream tasks and test different deployment env. that mimics the actual production line. Count use cases per model. Verification: deployment on test environment
Target Value	Response time value.

NFR aspect	NFR description
Name	Characteristic: Interaction Capability Sub-characteristics: Self-descriptiveness
Definition	Degree to which a product presents appropriate information, where needed by the user, to make its capabilities and use immediately obvious to the user without excessive interactions with a product or other resources (such as user documentation, help desks or other users).
Description	The system should contain enough information to be used without referring to documentation.
What is measured:	Ease of interaction and clarity of what is happening and how to interact.
KPI	User satisfaction with the interaction with the system.
Methods of collection/ measurement and verification/ validation	Running tests with selected users and evaluate satisfaction with an adequate feedback form. User satisfaction survey with a defined minimum of users.
Target Value	A predefined minimum satisfaction level score according to the given scale (e.g., satisfaction level of 8 on a scale from 1 to 10).

NFR aspect	NFR description
Name	Characteristic: Reliability Sub-characteristics: Fault tolerance
Definition	Degree to which a system, product or component operates as intended despite the presence of hardware or software faults.
Description	The system should continue to provide the expected output when a software or hardware fault arises.
What is measured:	Correspondence between provided output and expected output in presence of known faults.
KPI	The difference between output and expected output.
Methods of collection/ measurement and verification/ validation	Depends on the output type (unit, quantity). Injection of faults and stress test, or system log to analyse the behaviour in occurrence of a natural fault.
Target Value	The difference (in percentage [%]) of real output versus expected output in presence of a specific hardware or software fault (e.g., less than 10 % difference with expected output in presence of a specific HW or SW fault).

NFR aspect	NFR description
Name	Characteristic: Security Sub-characteristics: Confidentiality

Definition	Degree to which a product or system ensures that data are accessible only to those authorized to have access.
Description	Systems should implement mechanisms to prevent access to confidential data by unwanted entities (hackers/other users).
What is measured:	Number of successful attacks in which confidential data is accessed
KPI	Attack success rate = number of successful attacks over total number of attacks in a fixed period of time.
Methods of collection/ measurement and verification/ validation	Log files on system attacks or simulated attacks. Measure on the log files and/or after simulation.
Target Value	Maximum attack success rate [%] for a defined period of time (e.g., attack success rate < 0.001 %).

NFR aspect	NFR description
Name	Characteristics: Maintainability Sub-Characteristics: Modularity
Definition	Management Framework capable of serving AI models and updating them as needed, as well as scaling up types of supported sensory input.
Description	To develop an efficient, scalable, and maintainable Edge AI framework adaptable to various forms of sensory feedback.
What is measured:	Downtime required for maintenance and updates.
KPI	Time required for maintenance and updates.
Methods of collection/ measurement and verification/ validation	Measurement of time during live deployment.
Target Value	Maximum downtime [min] required for maintenance and updates (e.g., under 30 minutes of downtime).

NFR aspect	NFR description
Name	Characteristics: Flexibility Sub-Characteristics: Adaptability
Definition	Degree to which a system or product can effectively/efficiently be adapted for different or evolving HW/SW or other operational/usage environments.
Description	Adaptability to the evolving AI-based algorithms running on the HW/SW architecture.
What is measured	Types of AI-based algorithms running on the platform.
KPI	Qualitative [Times].
Methods of collection/ measurement and verification/ validation	Demonstrator evaluation. Validation of the types of AI-based algorithms running on the intelligent gateway.
Target Value	The increased number of AI-based algorithms that can be run on the platform in the end of the project compared to the start of the project (e.g., types of AI-based algorithms increased with 3 times from the start to the end of the project).

5. Edge AI Functional Requirements

5.1. Definition

The edge AI field has emerged in recent years, and there is no specific standardised definition exclusively for edge AI system functional requirements (FRs) in ISO or IEEE standards. The concept of functional requirements for systems, including those incorporating AI, can be framed within the broader context of requirements engineering and system functionalities described in existing standards. This deliverable aims to apply the principles of systems and software, hardware, AI, and data engineering standards. These requirements would focus on what functions an edge AI system must perform, considering its unique characteristics, such as local data processing, minimal latency, and resource constraints.

In this context, edge AI system functional requirements are specifications of what an edge AI system is supposed to do, describing the functions or tasks that the edge AI system must perform to meet its designated operations or to fulfil the needs of its users. These requirements define the behaviours, operations, and processes an edge AI system must execute to satisfy its intended purposes.

Functional requirements are crucial in edge AI systems, which combine hardware, software, AI components, and data development. They clearly describe what needs to be built and serve as a foundation for the edge AI system verification, validation, testing and benchmarking. They typically include inputs, expected outcomes, data handling, processing logic, and interactions with other systems.

Functional requirements describe what an edge AI system, application, or product must do to fulfil its intended purpose. They detail the edge AI system's specific behaviours, functions, and interactions under various conditions. Functional requirements guide the development process and ensure the final edge AI system (product, algorithm, model) meets user needs and business objectives.

When creating edge AI functional requirements, it is vital to remember that they should be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART). By following these guidelines, developers can be sure that the functional requirements are precise and will help edge AI development build the right system.

When defining the edge AI functional requirements, the designers must describe the KPIs and quantitative and qualitative target measures that are verifiable and follow the SMART criteria. Several considerations should be followed when describing edge AI functional requirements, such as being clearly and precisely described to avoid ambiguity and misunderstandings, feasible considering the technological, time, and resource constraints of the system, written in a way that they can be verified through testing or demonstration and relevant to the users' needs and align with the overall objectives of the edge AI system being developed.

Using the information provided in [24] functional requirements for edge AI systems are specifying what the item should do, aligning to the Functional Suitability quality characteristic outlined in ISO/IEC 25010 System and software quality models.

5.2. Edge AI functional requirements, KPIs and measures.

The following section provides examples structured in tables of edge AI functional requirements, key KPIs, and measures that researchers and practitioners can use as references for their projects.

AI algorithms

FR aspect	FR description
Name	AI algorithms
Definition	AI pattern recognition learning algorithms based on RGB Camera data input in natural environment.
Description	Pattern recognition capabilities – AI algorithms identifying grapes in a 2D RGB image.
What is measured	Measure the effective estimated patterns count.
KPI	Pattern recognition algorithms.
Methods of collection/ measurement and verification/ validation	Use of edge device on the autonomous system during the relevant growth period. Strict and manageable manual patterns counting. Comparison with AI estimated counting.
Target value	Yield estimation deviation (in percentage [%]) based on pattern recognition algorithms compared with actual yield (e.g., estimate yield with an error estimation less than 15 %).

FR aspect	FR description
Name	Improved perception
Definition	Perception is the ability of a robot to perceive and understand its environment
Description	Increase in perception quality in deployment area measured with relevant metric
What is measured:	Quality of human action classification
KPI	Mean average-precision (MAP)
Methods of collection/ measurement and verification/ validation	Academic benchmark data. Standard generalization tests on out-of-distribution data.
Target Value	Increase in precision compared to state-of-the-art on edge devices. (e.g., +25 increase in mIoU (mean intersection over union) with respect to state-of-the-art on edge devices).

FR aspect	FR description
Name	Real Time Functioning
Definition	To enable real-time use and dynamic learning by minimising time and resource requirements.
Description	Near real-time operation is important for overall user experience and usability of the integrated system.
What is measured:	Inference time, end-to-end latency of the system.

KPI	System Latency.
Methods of collection/ measurement and verification/ validation	Live Demonstration.
Target Value	Low system latency (near real-time operation if required by the functionality) (e.g., dependent on each functionality (2-60 sec)).

FR aspect	FR description
Name	Video processing real-time
Definition	In a vision-based AI system, input data often comes in form of a video stream with a certain frequency (e.g. 25 frames per second or fps). The system is said to be “video-real-time” if it can process each frame before the next frame arrives in the input.
Description	The video speed induces an available time budget for each frame inversely proportional to the frame rate. The system is said video real time if the processing time of one frame does not exceed the available time budget for each frame.
What is measured:	Time necessary to process one frame.
KPI	Proportion of the time budget used to process one frame.
Methods of collection/ measurement and verification/ validation	Test run with benchmark of video input.
Target Value	One frame process time versus time budget versus in percentage [%] (e.g., proportion of time budget < 100 %).

FR aspect	FR description
Name	Resolution of input images
Definition	Edge AI algorithms have limited resources and are able to process images only up to a certain size or resolution. In the case where the input resolution is variable, this functional requirement specifies what is the maximum resolution that the system should be able to process.
Description	Highest image resolution that the system can process.
What is measured:	Correct behaviour of the system with a certain resolution image.
KPI	Max image size.
Methods of collection/ measurement and verification/ validation	Test run with benchmark of image input.
Target Value	Increased maximum image resolution while maintain correct behaviour compared to baseline/starting point (e.g., size up to 1024 x 1024 pixels).

FR aspect	FR description
Name	Extensibility of the optimization to various types of Neural Networks
Definition	The optimization shall be extensible to allow the optimization to be applicable to various types of Neural Networks.
Description	The optimization algorithm shall be extensible to support various types of Neural Networks, including: CNNs, LSTMs and Transformer models.

What is measured:	The ability of the optimization algorithm to optimize various types of Neural Network architectures.
KPI	Achieved / Not achieved [Qualitative].
Methods of collection/ measurement and verification/ validation	Optimization runs applied to the specified types of Neural Networks. Results showing optimized models for the above specified types of Neural Networks.
Target Value	Shown applicability of the optimization to the above specified types of Neural Networks.

6. Ethical and Legal Considerations

AI technology evolves, and the ethical and legal considerations surrounding its deployment have received significant attention from stakeholders, policymakers, ethicists, and technologists. The ongoing discussions revolve around ensuring that AI systems are performant, effective and aligned with fundamental human rights, societal values, and legal frameworks. These considerations encompass accountability, transparency, bias, privacy, and security, essential for fostering trust and acceptance of AI and edge AI technologies.

One of the primary ethical concerns in AI revolves around accountability. As AI systems increasingly make decisions affecting humans, determining who is responsible for potential harm or errors becomes crucial. This is particularly relevant in high-stakes domains such as healthcare and autonomous vehicles. Ethical frameworks for AI should establish clear lines of accountability among developers, deployers, and users, ensuring that parties can be held responsible for the impacts of AI decisions. The European Union AI Act addresses this concern by mandating that providers of high-risk AI systems ensure human oversight and establish accountability mechanisms, thereby fostering a culture of responsibility in AI development and deployment.

Transparency is another fundamental ethical consideration. The black-box nature of many AI systems often obscures how decisions are made, leading to a lack of understanding among users and affected parties. Transparency is essential for building trust and enabling stakeholders to challenge and understand AI-generated outcomes. The EU AI Act emphasises transparency by requiring users to be informed when interacting with AI systems. Furthermore, the Act mandates clear and understandable information about system capabilities and limitations for high-risk AI systems, enhancing user awareness and informed consent.

Bias and discrimination represent critical ethical concerns in AI systems. Algorithms can inadvertently perpetuate and reinforce societal biases present in the data used to train them, leading to unfair outcomes for different groups. Developing fair and unbiased AI systems is important for ethical integrity and social justice. The EU AI Act addresses this by requiring risk assessments for high-risk AI systems to identify and mitigate potential bias and discrimination, thereby promoting fairness in AI deployments.

Privacy and data protection are also central ethical and legal considerations. AI systems often rely on vast amounts of personal data to function effectively, raising concerns about user privacy and data security. The alignment with existing legal frameworks, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), is essential to ensure that data collection and processing practices comply with individuals' rights. The EU AI Act reinforces this alignment, mandating that AI systems be designed

in accordance with privacy principles and ensuring that personal data is processed lawfully and transparently.

Security considerations are equally important, particularly in the context of AI systems deployed in critical sectors such as finance, infrastructure, and healthcare. Malicious attacks on AI systems can have severe consequences, making security an integral part of AI's ethical and legal landscape. The EU AI Act requires that high-risk AI systems undergo rigorous conformity assessments to verify their security and reliability before they can be placed on the market. This proactive approach helps ensure the robustness of AI systems and enhances public confidence in their use.

The ethical and legal considerations in AI are not only about compliance but also about fostering innovation and societal benefit. As AI technologies offer transformative potential across various sectors, balancing innovation with ethical responsibility is vital. The EU AI Act aims to provide a regulatory framework that supports innovation while safeguarding fundamental rights and promoting ethical AI development.

By aligning ethical considerations with legal frameworks, the EU AI Act aims to create a cohesive approach to AI regulation that positions the European Union as a leader in fostering responsible AI. The Act adopts a risk-based approach, categorising AI systems into different risk levels and applying appropriate regulatory measures accordingly. This perspective allows for flexibility and adaptability, providing a robust framework that encourages ethical AI deployment while ensuring legal compliance.

AI ethical and legal considerations are increasingly important, as highlighted by the implementation of the EU AI Act, which serves as a reference point for balancing technical development with ethical responsibility. By addressing accountability, transparency, bias, privacy, and security, the Act aligns with fundamental ethical principles and establishes a legal framework that ensures safe and responsible AI deployment in society. As the landscape of AI continues to evolve, ongoing dialogue and collaboration among stakeholders will be essential in navigating the ethical and legal challenges and supporting the development of AI technologies to benefit the users while upholding its values and rights.

Edge AI introduces ethical and legal considerations based on its decentralised nature and proximity to data sources. Edge AI handles sensitive personal data closer to users, requiring strict adherence to data protection regulations. Given the risks of unauthorised access or misuse, ensuring data is processed securely and with user consent becomes paramount. Accountability is important as decisions are made locally on edge devices; determining who is responsible for errors or harmful outcomes can be challenging. This fragmentation of responsibility complicates traditional legal frameworks that typically attribute liability to central providers.

Legal considerations include compliance with data protection regulations across various jurisdictions, as edge AI systems may operate across geographical. The potential for Edge AI to enable real-time decision-making in critical applications such as autonomous vehicles or healthcare devices introduces liability concerns that need careful legal consideration.

Bias and fairness remain important ethical issues, as edge AI systems may evolve based on local data that could be skewed or unrepresentative as localised training or decision-making might lead to inconsistent outcomes across edge devices. Addressing these biases is essential to prevent

discrimination in applications like healthcare and facial recognition. Transparency is also a concern, as users need clear information about how edge AI systems operate, especially regarding the processes behind essential decisions. The security of edge AI devices deserves attention, as vulnerabilities can expose networks to cyber threats.

7. Standards

7.1. AI Standards

AI standardisation activities are receiving attention across various Standard Development Organizations (SDOs) to address the diverse challenges and opportunities AI technologies present. These SDOs include international bodies such as the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), and regional organisations like the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI).

ISO and IEC are collaborating on a joint technical committee (JTC 1) that focuses on standardising AI across different dimensions, such as terminology, risk management, and ethical considerations. This committee has initiated the development of standards that outline best practices for AI implementation, ensuring interoperability, safety, and reliability in AI systems. Their work also emphasises the importance of transparency and accountability, with an aim to facilitate trust in AI technologies among users and stakeholders.

The IEEE has established its Global Initiative 2.0 on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems, striving to lead standardisation activities that promote ethical considerations and inclusive practices in AI development. Through initiatives like the IEEE 7010 series, which focuses on the ethical considerations of autonomous systems, IEEE addresses challenges specific to AI, such as real-time processing, and the safe deployment of AI algorithms in edge environments. These standards emphasise the importance of reliability and resilience in AI applications.

IEEE's efforts focus on creating standards that guide technical aspects and encompass values such as fairness, accountability, and privacy. Their extensive engagement with industry stakeholders, academia, and policymakers aims to address the societal impacts of AI technologies and ensure that standards reflect diverse perspectives.

ETSI is also actively involved in AI standardisation, particularly in relation to telecommunications and the Internet of Things (IoT). It is working on frameworks that facilitate the integration of AI into network and service management while addressing security and privacy challenges. By providing guidelines and standards, ETSI aims to enhance the deployment of AI-driven solutions within its domains, fostering innovation while ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements.

Moreover, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has developed principles for AI that focus on promoting AI's beneficial use while addressing its potential risks. These principles serve as a foundation for member countries to consider in their policymaking and standardisation efforts.

AI standardisation activities across SDOs are multifaceted, addressing technical, ethical, and societal dimensions of AI technologies. The SDOs are working collaboratively to create frameworks and guidelines that ensure AI systems are safe, reliable, transparent, and aligned with ethical principles, thereby laying the groundwork for responsible innovation in the AI landscape.

The standards and standardisation activities address AI technology and applications and are not focusing specific at edge AI. However, this is changing as edge AI is emerging as a critical focus area due to the increasing adoption of decentralised computing models. This approach requires to address factors such as latency, bandwidth limitations, and data privacy.

Table 7-1 lists the primary AI standards and standardisation activities in the standard development organisations mentioned before.

Table 7-1 Relevant AI standards and standardization activities

ITU-T - International Telecommunication Union - Telecommunication Standardization Sector	
Y.Suppl.63 to ITU-T Y.4000	Unlocking the Internet of Things with artificial intelligence: Where we are and where we could be.
CEN/CENELEC - European Committee for Normalization / European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization	
FG on AI	Focus Group on Artificial Intelligence. It was the first and only contributor on AI topics in CEN and created a set of interesting documents on first ideas on AI (late 2010') later superseded by a CEN/CLC JTC 21 on AI.
JTC 21	Joint Technical Committee 21 'Artificial Intelligence'. It identifies and adopts international standards already available or under development from other organizations like ISO/IEC JTC 1 and its subcommittees, such as SC 42 Artificial Intelligence. Furthermore, it focuses on producing standardization deliverables that address European market and societal needs, as well as underpinning EU legislation, policies, principles, and values.
ISO/IEC - International Organization for Standards / International Electrotechnical Commission	
JTC 1/SC 42	Artificial Intelligence. This overarching JTC focuses on different aspects of AI, produces a set of standards (among which the ISO/IEC 8183: Artificial intelligence - Data life cycle framework) and is composed of a set of WGs.
WG 1	Foundational standards.
WG 3	Trustworthiness.
WG 4	Use cases and applications.
WG 5	Computational approaches and characteristics of artificial intelligence systems.
JWG 4	It administers several Joint WGs with other subcommittees e.g., with IEC TC65/SC65A: Functional safety and AI systems.
TR 24027	Information technology - Artificial Intelligence (AI) – Bias in AI systems and AI-aided decision making.
TR 24028:2020	Information technology - Artificial intelligence — Overview of trustworthiness in artificial intelligence.
DTR 24029-1	Artificial Intelligence (AI) - Assessment of the robustness of neural networks — Part 1: Overview.
AWI 24029-2	Artificial Intelligence (AI) - Assessment of the robustness of neural networks — Part 2: Methodology for the use of formal methods.
WD 5259-1	Data quality for analytics and ML — Part 1: Overview, terminology, and examples.
WD 5259-2	Data quality for analytics and ML — Part 2: Data quality measures
WD 5259-3	Data quality for analytics and ML — Part 3: Data quality management requirements and guidelines.
WD 5259-4	Data quality for analytics and ML — Part 4: Data quality process framework
WD 5338	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — AI system life cycle processes.
AWI TR 24368	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of ethical and societal concerns.

AWI TR 24372	Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) - Overview of computational approaches for AI systems.
25012:2008	Software engineering — Software product Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) — Data quality model.
WD TS 4213	Information technology — Artificial Intelligence — Assessment of machine learning classification performance.
23894:2023	Information Technology – Artificial Intelligence – Guidance on Risk Management.
WD 42001	Information Technology — Artificial intelligence — Management system.
AWI 25059	Software engineering — Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) - Quality model for AI-based systems.
ETSI - European Telecommunications Standards Institute	
OCG AI	Co-ordination Group on Artificial Intelligence. It acts as a coordination group for the standardisation activities related to AI handled in the technical bodies and committees and ISGs of ETSI.
ISG ENI	Industry Specification Group Experiential Network Intelligence. It focuses on leveraging AI methods to increase the dynamicity, adaptability and reaction of telecommunication networks and its acting entities, and on the following MARS-related topics: develop standards for a Cognitive Network Management system, incorporating one or more closed control loops; provide a telemetry processing framework that uses context and situation awareness to learn and reason about which data should be collected using what types of processing mechanisms to support information collection and measurement about network performance, network resources and services.
IEEE SA- Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Standard Association	
A-IS	Autonomous and Intelligent Systems. It ensures that every stakeholder involved in the design and development of autonomous and intelligent systems is educated, trained, and empowered to prioritize ethical considerations so that these technologies are advanced for the benefit of humanity.
ECPAIS	Ethics Certification Program for Autonomous and Intelligent Systems. It focuses on certification and marking processes that advance transparency, accountability, and reduction in algorithmic bias in (A-IS).
P3333.1.3	Standard for the Deep Learning-Based Assessment of Visual Experience Based on Human Factors.
P3652.1-2020	Guide for Architectural Framework and Application of Federated Machine Learning.
P2805.3	Cloud-Edge Collaboration Protocols for Machine Learning. It specifies the collaboration protocols of enabling ML on the edge computing node with support from industrial clouds and provides implementation reference for ML on lower powered, cheaper, embedded devices.
P2961	Guide for an Architectural Framework and Application for Collaborative Edge Computing. It defines a ML framework that allows a computing task to be decomposed and distributed across edge and cloud nodes, the architectural framework and application guidelines for collaborative edge computing, and provides a blueprint for data usage, ML, and computing collaboration in edge computing environments.

7.1.1. Spatial web standards

The IEEE P2874 Spatial Web Standard defines protocol, architecture, and governance specifications for a reference model of the Spatial Web, a system designed to integrate physical and virtual environments into a globally accessible, interoperable, and governable framework [58]. This standard addresses the convergence of edge decentralized technologies, i.e., extended reality (XR), artificial intelligence (AI), autonomous systems, robotics, and the Internet of Things (IoT) to create a cohesive cyber-physical ecosystem [58]. It serves as a foundation for future implementation specifications and domain-specific architectures.

As a sociotechnical standard, the IEEE P2874 Spatial Web Standard aims to address the following key requirements:

- **Semantic Interoperability:** Establish a shared ontological framework for representing and exchanging meaning between human and AI agents within the Spatial Web.
- **System Explainability:** Enable the modelling and representation of intelligent agent activities and decision-making to enhance transparency and accountability.
- **Cross-Domain Interoperability:** Facilitate universal data and model interoperability in the continuum compute to enable collaboration across organizational, network, and jurisdictional boundaries.
- **Regulatory Compliance:** Ensure adherence to diverse local, regional, national, and international regulations, cultural norms, and ethical standards through built-in governance mechanisms.
- **Identity and Access Management:** Implement decentralized authentication and credentialing systems with privacy and security safeguards to enable fine-grained control over system activities and resources.
- **Multi-Scale Cognitive Computing:** Support distributed, multi-agent AI systems operating across various scales of the Spatial Web ecosystem.
- **Polycentric Governance:** Enable flexible, context-specific governance models that can adapt to diverse domains and use cases within the Spatial Web.
- **Hyperspace Representation:** Provide a framework for representing and navigating multi-dimensional spaces, including physical, virtual, and abstract domains.
- **Real-time Interaction:** Support low-latency, high-fidelity interactions between users, AI agents, and digital twins across the Spatial Web.

The IEEE P2874 system requirement specifications encompass the definition of the Hyperspatial Modelling Language (HSML) and the Hyperspatial Transaction Protocol (HSTP), along with the Universal Domain Graph (UDG) and a governance framework designed to address ethical, legal, and social considerations in several context such as AI and the deployment of autonomous technologies at the Edge.

7.1.1.1 HSML

HSML is a knowledge model that represents the conceptual entities defining the system and the relationships between these entities. The Spatial Web offers a knowledge structure for domains within both the physical and digital worlds, modelling any domain as a graph structure encoded in HSML. For example, HSML defines representations of hyperspace, including those of physical edge spaces. Figure 7-1 illustrates the HSML knowledge model [58].

Figure 7-1: HSML knowledge model.

7.1.1.2 UDG

The Universal Domain Graph (UDG) refers to the interconnected network of graphs from all domains within both the physical and digital worlds, along with their relationships within the Spatial Web. A domain is defined as an entity with a persistent identity endowed with rights and credentials over time. A Domain Authority is an entity credentialed to define the norms and terms governing actors, actions, and credentials within that domain. The UDG comprises nodes representing entities and links representing the relationships between these entities. The UDG is intended to be a publicly accessible knowledge graph, serving as a critical infrastructure component of the Spatial Web [58].

7.1.1.3 HSTP

HSTP enables nodes, ranging from edge to cloud, to communicate with one another to execute functions and share HSML data. It is an application-layer, generic, and generalizable protocol designed to standardize communication between systems, essential for building a coherent, decentralized, secure, and privacy-respecting Spatial Web. HSTP is compatible with multiple protocol bindings, which facilitate communication and data transfer between edge systems in various contexts. HSTP allows compliant systems to communicate effectively, regardless of the specific protocol binding, by providing a standard semantic layer for these protocol bindings. This ensures a consistent and standardized approach to exchanging information and executing functions across different types of systems and applications. HSTP sends messages as HSTP Operations, which are transmitted over a transport protocol. These requests and responses are encoded using profile encoding formats defined by the HSML Implementation Specification [58].

7.1.1.4 Governance

Future technologies must be able to represent rules and laws within their domains in a way that both humans and machines deployed in any domain can interpret. Traditionally, rules and regulations have been drafted by humans for human interpretation, with little consideration for machine interpretability and executability. Bridging this gap by creating machine-readable and

machine-executable regulations offers significant value, ensuring that machines and AI systems universally adhere to the same rules and regulations.

To accurately represent laws, the Spatial Web must be organized in a hierarchical, nested architecture where rules are inherited from higher levels and passed down to lower ones until edge systems, like how state laws take precedence over regional or domain-specific laws. Domain authorities shall define the norms and terms for creating contracts within a given domain, governing actors and actions.

This structure would enable regulators to make real-time updates to rules, allowing lower-level entities on the edge to adapt dynamically to factors like weather conditions. In essence, the Spatial Web provides the specifications and the framework for industry leaders and regulators to create, regulate, and manage industry-specific domains [58].

8. Conclusion

This deliverable explores functional and non-functional requirements for edge AI systems, providing a comprehensive framework for understanding and implementing these advanced technologies across the micro-, deep-, and meta-edge continuum. It provides a holistic approach to edge AI system development and deployment by intertwining the concepts of dependability and trustworthiness with these requirements.

The shift towards edge AI represents a significant evolution in AI technology, offering solutions to challenges posed by centralised systems, such as latency, bandwidth limitations, and privacy concerns. However, this transition also introduces new complexities and considerations that must be carefully addressed to ensure the successful implementation of edge AI systems.

The detailed examination of functional requirements highlights the critical capabilities for edge AI systems to perform effectively in diverse, often resource-constrained environments. These include real-time processing, energy efficiency, and adaptive learning capabilities. Equally important are the non-functional requirements, which encompass a wide range of quality attributes from reliability and security to more AI-specific considerations like explainability and fairness.

By linking these requirements to the concepts of dependability and trustworthiness, the deliverable underscores the importance of creating edge AI systems that are functionally effective, reliable, secure, and aligned with ethical standards and societal values. This approach recognises that the success of edge AI deployments hinges not just on technical performance but also on the ability to build and maintain trust with users and stakeholders.

Discussing Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and measurement methods provides practical guidance for assessing and monitoring edge AI systems. This focus on quantifiable metrics and ongoing assessment is crucial for maintaining system performance and adapting to changing requirements over time.

The framework presented in this deliverable offers a foundation for future research and development in edge AI. It highlights areas where further innovation is needed, particularly in

addressing the unique challenges of edge environments, such as limited computational resources and intermittent connectivity.

Moreover, the emphasis on ethical considerations and alignment with societal values points to the need for ongoing dialogue between technologists, policymakers, and the public. Ensuring their trustworthiness and societal acceptance will be important as edge AI systems become more prevalent in critical applications.

The comprehensive exploration of edge AI requirements provides a valuable resource for researchers, developers, and decision-makers in the field. Offering a structured approach to understanding and implementing edge AI systems contributes to the responsible advancement of this continuously changing technology. As edge AI continues to evolve, the principles and frameworks outlined in this paper will serve as essential guides for creating systems that are not only technologically advanced but also dependable, trustworthy, and aligned with broader societal goals.

The deliverable is currently being extended to include more details and definitions and will be published as a monograph in this year by River Publishers, Denmark. The publication will be the Open Access and available both online and in printing format. The publication is a detailed written study focused on functional and non-functional requirements for edge AI systems to provide an overview of current state of play, concepts, definitions, taxonomy and gaps in the field.

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